

Acknowledgement

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References

1. H. N. FOX, *Science*, 1952, 116, 129; R. B. PATHAK and S. C. BAHEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 1108; T. IRIKUPA, Jap. Pat. 7 570 367/1975 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1976, 84, 59445); U. WRZECIONO, K. PIETKIEWIEZ and B. KRZYAZTO, *Pharmazie*, 1978, 33, 266; J. F. W. MCOMIE and R. N. FIMMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 92.
2. R. G. CHILD, R. G. WILKINSON and A. T. FUCIK, US Pat. 4 006 234/1977 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1977, 87, 6031); I. M. ROUSHADI, E. S. A. IBRAHIM and H. S. HABIB, *Pharmazie*, 1956, 31, 856; K. N. GAIND and J. M. KHANNA, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1964, 26, 34; L. S. GOODMAN and A. GILMAN, "The Pharmacological Basis of Therapeutics", 4th. ed., Macmillan, New York, 1970, p. 1111; J. L. EVERETT and W. C. J. ROSS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1972.
3. R. JAIN and P. PANDEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, communicated.

Synthesis of some New Fluorinated Derivatives of 1,3,5-Triazine as Potential Biologically Active Agents

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SOME 1,3,5-triazine derivatives have been reported to exhibit interesting biological activities¹. In view of the biological activity, we have synthesised (Scheme 1) and characterised a number of new 2-(arylanilino)-4-(2-chloro-5-trifluoromethylani-lino)-6-(3-nitroanilino)-1,3,5-triazine derivatives

Scheme 1

These compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against *E. coli* and *S. aureus* by paper disc method². All the compounds exhibited significant activity against *S. aureus*, however, no activity against *E. coli* (Table 1).

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected, and the purity was checked by tlc. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, ¹H and ¹⁹F nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆; TMS as an internal standard for ¹H and C₆F₆ as an external standard for ¹⁹F) on a FX 93Q JEOL spectrometer (90 MHz).

2,4-Dichloro-6-(3-nitroanilino)-1,3,5-triazine (1): To 2,4,6-trichloro-1,3,5-triazine (5.53 g, 0.03 mol) dissolved in acetone (30 ml) was added a solution of *m*-nitroaniline (4.14 g, 0.03 mol) in acetone (10 ml) with stirring at 0–5° followed by the addition of NaOH solution (1.2 g, 0.03 mol in 10 ml of water). The reaction mixture was stirred for further 3 h at 0–5°. It was then poured into ice-cold water and acidified with HCl. The resulting solid was washed,

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3

Sl. no.	Ar	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %	Zone of inhibition (mm) <i>S. aureus</i>
1.	<i>p</i> -COOH C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ ClF ₃ N ₇ O ₄	158	60	7.0
2.	<i>m</i> -COOH C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ ClF ₃ N ₇ O ₄	180	61	6.0
3.	<i>m</i> -Cl C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ F ₃ N ₇ O ₂	160	90	6.0
4.	<i>m</i> -OH C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ ClF ₃ N ₇ O ₃	145	60	8.0
5.	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ ClF ₃ N ₇ O ₄	210	70	7.0
6.	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ ClF ₃ N ₇ O ₂	115	65	7.0
7.	<i>o</i> -OC ₂ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ ClF ₃ N ₇ O ₂	118	60	7.0
8.	C ₁₀ H ₇	C ₂₆ H ₁₇ ClF ₃ N ₇ O ₂	190	61	6.0
9.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ ClF ₃ N ₇ O ₂	202	63	7.0
10.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ ClF ₃ N ₇ O ₄	220	60	7.0

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

NOTES

TABLE 2—IR, ¹H AND ¹⁹F NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3

Sl. no	ν_{max} (KBr; cm^{-1})				¹ H δ (DMSO-d ₆ ; from TMS)			¹⁹ F δ	
	NH (br)	C ₅ N ₃	C-Cl	CF ₃ (asym.) (sym.)	C-NO ⁺ (asym.) (sym.)	NH (m)	ArH (m)		COOH OH OCH ₂ OCH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂
1.	3 360-3 110	820	795	1 125, 1 170 1 330	1 570 1 345	9 65-10.18	7 17-8.84	10 96(s)	-55.54
2.	3 380-3 100	800	770	1 125, 1 170 1 330	1 580 1 345	9 41-10.06	7 31-8.79	10 92(s)	-56 20
3.	3 380-3 100	805	775	1 125, 1 170 1 330	1 575 1 335	9.39-10.03	7.38-8.85	—	-55.48
4.	3 360-3 100	800	775	1 125, 1 170 1 330	1 570 1 335	9.61-10.05	7.38-8 81	9 61-10.05	-55.48
5.	3 360-3 120	815	795	1 130, 1 165 1 330	1 565 1 335	9.81-10.89	7.34-8 81	—	-55.54
6.	3 370-3 120	800	770	1 130, 1 170 1 330	1 575 1 345	9.85-10.12	7 03-8.78	3.88(s)	-55.18
7.	3 370-3 110	800	795	1 120, 1 165 1 330	1 570 1 340	9.95-10.89	6.59-8.14	4.12(q) 1.44(t)	-55.77
8.	3 360-3 100	800	775	1 125, 1 165 1 330	1 570 1 345	9 85-10.45	6.64-8 10	—	-55.57
9.	3 360-3 110	800	775	1 125, 1 165 1 330	1 575 1 340	9.15-10.05	6.62-8 20	2.68(s)	-56.57
10.	3 370-3 100	800	775	1 125, 1 170 1 330	1 575 1 340	9.78-10.85	7 30-8.84	—	-55.77

br = broad, s = singlet, m = multiplet, asym. = asymmetry, sym. = symmetry

dried and recrystallised from ethanol, (7.98 g, 93%), m.p. 259°.

2-Chloro-4-(2-chloro-5-trifluoromethylanilino)-6-(3-nitroanilino)-1,3,5-triazine (2): To 1 (3.43 g, 0.012 mol) dissolved in acetone (40 ml) was added a solution of 3-amino-4-chlorobenzotrifluoride (2.35 g, 0.012 mol) in acetone (10 ml) with continuous stirring followed by the addition of NaOH solution (0.48 g, 0.012 mol in 10 ml of water). It was stirred for 3 h at 30-35°. After cooling, the reaction mixture was poured into ice-cold water and acidified with HCl. The resulting solid was washed, dried and recrystallised from ethanol, (4.33 g, 81%), m.p. 230°.

2-(Arylanilino)-4-(2-chloro-5-trifluoromethylanilino)-6-(3-nitroanilino)-1,3,5-triazine (3): To 2 (0.003 mol) dissolved in 1,4-dioxane (6 ml), the solution of different aromatic amines (0.003 mol) in dioxane (6 ml) was added slowly followed by the addition of NaOH solution (0.003 mole in 5 ml of water). It was then heated for 3 h at 85-90°. After cooling, it was poured into ice-cold water. The resulting solid was washed, dried and recrystallised from ethanol (Tables 1 and 2).

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References

1. F. H. S. CURD, J. K. LANDQUIST and F. L. ROSE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 154; R. R. ANDREOLI, P. P. LLIVERAS, P. J. RIUS and C. L. MENDIETA, *Spad*,

Pat. 510 97C/1983 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1983, 99, 88237); CIBA Ltd., Brit Pat 754 071/1956 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1957, 51, 8814); U.S. Pat. 2 824 088/1958 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1958, 52, 61176); A. KREUTZBERGER and M. LOCH, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1986, 319, 275; N. C. DESAI, H. K. SHUKLA and K. A. THAPER, *J. Inst. Chem. (Calcutta)*, 1984, 56, 137

2. R. S. VARMA and W. L. NOBLES, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1972, 61, 112.

Determination of Bismuth at Parts per Million Levels in Rocks and Minerals by Flame Atomic Absorption Spectrometry

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FLAME atomic absorption methods for determination of bismuth at ppm levels in geological materials are subject to serious matrix interferences and their sensitivity is also not sufficient to permit direct measurements at such low levels^{1,2}. Donaldson³ proposed a Flame AAS method for determination of bismuth employing DDTC-chloroform extraction for removal of interferences, and proposed⁴ an iodide extraction method with improved performance. This method is also subject to interference from copper and lead, if present in large amounts. We have found that Flame AAS measurements directly from the organic phase provide much better sensitivity without any